
Deliverable Number 9.1

Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Version 3 (M38)

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History of Revisions

Version, Date	Summary of changes made
V1, 5.9.16 (M5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaption of DEP developed at application stages • Validated and approved by consortium (29.8.16)
V2, 28.6.17 (M14)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of Data Management Plan • Revision of protocols (p2) • DOI (Zenodo reference) added • Replacement of partner name HWU with UEDIN • Revision of Publications and Research Outputs protocol – related to DMP (p9) • Typographical edits • Validated and approved by consortium (28.6.17)
V3, 13.06.19 (M38)	<p>December 2018 – January 2019:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated names of WP9 personnel (Manager and AquaTT contact person) • Clarification of reporting instructions (pre & post publication requirements) (section 3,4) • Inclusion of GDPR protocol (p8) • Revision of Knowledge Management section (p24) • Inclusion new dissemination resources and tools (p22) • Revision of Stakeholder Engagement (section 7) • New guidelines for public engagement (p30) • Correction of formatting errors, structure and typographical errors • Last revision 20.12.18 (V3) sent to consortium (20.12.18). • Reviewed by the consortium M33 (16.01.19)
	<p>January – June 2019:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revision of Prior Notice period and protocols (p7, p9) based on amendment to Consortium Agreement (M33) (agreed by ATLAS Steering Committee on 31.1.19 AMD-678760-37) • Another revision of Knowledge Management section based on feedback from Project Coordinator at review phase (section 7) • Updated dissemination statistics (p18) • Inclusion new dissemination channels (research gate (p19)) • Revision of Code of Social Media conduct (p20) • Addition of ATLAS Outreach Educational Portfolio (p22, 29) • Correction of formatting errors, structure and typographical errors • Validated by the consortium M38 (21.06.19)

Executive Summary

Objectives

The ATLAS Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) describes the activities to be performed and the dissemination and exploitation means to be used in order to promote ATLAS and exploit the project results. It is a dynamic document and therefore updated periodically. The current version is the third update which was finalised in M38 (June 2019). The updated version (V3) includes clarified protocols regarding knowledge management and communication strategies as well as adjustments according to feedback from the first phase of the project to ensure effectiveness of efforts going forward.

Rationale

The ATLAS DEP outlines the EC rights and obligations of the consortium related to project results, identifies the key project stakeholders, defines the communication and dissemination channels and describes the means (tools, messages) of dissemination. In addition, it describes the internal process and protocols set up to manage the knowledge outputs and to ensure exploitation of ATLAS results. The protocols are set up to:

- a) Disseminate the ATLAS project and its results, ensuring information provision and awareness raising.
- b) Collect, analyse and transfer research outputs (e.g. products, methodologies, findings) to end-users who can make the best use of those results.
- c) Ensure ATLAS's results and Intellectual Property (IP) are properly managed.

ATLAS will develop and make use of the latest tools, resources and communication channels to ensure cost effectiveness and maximum impact.

Overall, Work Package (WP) 9 is tasked with ensuring effective external communication, dissemination and optimal outreach of ATLAS's results and applications to various stakeholders. It is closely linked to WP7 – Policy Integration to Inform Key Agreements; WP8 – Open Science Resources for Stakeholders; WP10 – Co-ordination and Management. Collectively the WPs work closely together to ensure effective exploitation of ATLAS research results.

The DEP has been developed and updated by AquaTT with input from the ATLAS Project Office (University of Edinburgh) and Dynamic Earth. All project partners have a role to play in dissemination and exploitation of the ATLAS project, its activities and outputs in order to foster awareness and transfer results for impact, especially in their own countries and in their own communities.

Team involved in deliverable writing and updates: AquaTT (Dr Annette Wilson, Dr Claudia Junge, Ms Georgia Bayliss-Brown, Ms Marieke Reuver, Mr David Murphy), ATLAS Project Office (Professor J Murray Roberts, Dr Katherine Simpson, Dr Laurence De Clippele, Ms Julia Eighteen), Dynamic Earth (Dr Hermione Cockburn, Dr Christine Angus, Ms Emma Paterson).

Reference on ZENODO:

Junge, Claudia, Reuver, Marieke, Murphy, David, Roberts, Murray J., Simpson, Katherine, De Clippele, Laurence, ... Pesant, Stéphane. (2016). ATLAS Deliverable 9.1 - Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.167409>

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1. Introduction

The ATLAS project aims to gather diverse new information on sensitive Atlantic ecosystems, to support a step-change in our understanding of their connectivity, functioning and responses to future changes in human use and ocean climate. To maximise the impacts of ATLAS and its results, the project has implemented effective communication, dissemination and knowledge transfer methodologies and strategies.

In order to measure the impact of ATLAS results, effective transfer of the new knowledge to different end-users (academia, industry, policy makers and wider society) is required. To achieve this, three dedicated work packages (WP7, WP8 and WP9) are involved in this task. The overall management and implementation of the DEP by WP9, is designed to support aims; (i) to reach high-level policymakers to translate science into policy to practice (WP7) and (ii) to improve the discoverability and reusability of research outputs by science, policy and industry stakeholders (WP8). Together these activities will lead to the widest exploitation of ATLAS research outputs: contributing to the Atlantic Action Plan initiatives on Ocean Literacy and further support development of the European Research Area and the Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance.

Specific Objectives:

- Adopt EC best practice communication guidelines and define the objectives, target end users, planned tools and channels, responsibilities and resources and metrics for measuring impact.
- Ensure there is an approved and transparent process to collect, analyse and transfer key ATLAS outputs to end-users who can make the best use of those results.
- Link with a Data Management Plan (DMP) including an open access data policy and data submission instructions.
- Promote the ATLAS project and its activities and results employing a range of communication and dissemination tools.
- Organise outreach exhibitions and workshops as tools to promote deep-sea research in general and specifically of ATLAS.
- Carry out effective dissemination of the scientific results.
- Ensure suitable Intellectual Property management strategies to enable effective knowledge transfer and innovation.

All project partners are involved in dissemination and exploitation in order to foster awareness and transfer results for impact, especially in their **own countries and in their own communities**.

The following partners in ATLAS have specifically time allocated to communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, according to the table below (in person months). Those in bold have greater than three person-months allocated to WP9 activities:

Partner	Partner name	Person-months in WP9
1	UEDIN	5
2	AU	1
3	IMAR-Uaz	1
5	NERC-BGS	5.48
7	IFREMER	0.5
8	MSS	0.5
9	UniHB	3.5
10	IODINE	1
11	NIOZ	2
12	DE	11.5
13	OXU	0.2
14	UCD	0.5
15	UCL	0.5
16	NUIG	3.75
17	ULIV	0.5
18	USD	3.5
19	UIT	1.5
20	SAMS	1.5
22	IEO	3.26
24	AquaTT	17.5

2. EC Rights and Obligations Related to Results

2.1 Ownership of Results

Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them. Two or more beneficiaries' own results jointly if they have jointly generated them and it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or separate them, for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection (see ATLAS Grant Agreement (GA) Article 27). The joint owners must agree (in writing) on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership ('joint ownership agreement'), to ensure compliance with their obligations under the GA. If valuable results are not protected the Commission may, under certain circumstances, assume ownership of the results (for further details, please consult GA Article 26).

2.2 Protection of Results

Each beneficiary has an obligation to protect its results. For any results that can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited, beneficiaries must examine the possibility of protecting them and if possible, protect them even if this requires further research and development or private investment. If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, to stop protecting them or not seek an extension of protection, the EU may under certain conditions (see Article 26.4) assume ownership to ensure their (continued) protection.

2.3 Exploitation of Results

Under Horizon 2020, beneficiaries should engage in dissemination and exploitation activities, aiming for the fruits of research to reach society as a whole. Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers. By sharing research results with the rest of the scientific community, the project contributes to the progress of science in genera. Exploitation is the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking.

Each beneficiary has an obligation to exploit its results. Each beneficiary must – up to four years after the period set out in GA Article 3 – take measures aiming to ensure 'exploitation' of its results by: (a) using them in further research activities; (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process; (c) creating and providing a service, or (d) using them in standardisation activities. For further details, please consult GA Article 28. If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced in accordance with GA Article 43.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and Management

The ATLAS Consortium Agreement (CA) follows the standard rules as outlined in the DESCA (Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement) model for Horizon 2020, which defines the main approach regarding the ownership, protection and access to key knowledge like IPR and data. These approaches are set out to allow ATLAS to collectively and individually pursue market opportunities arising from the project's results. ATLAS will follow the rules for IP set out by the EC, as regulated and agreed upon by all partners (by written signature) in the CA.

More information can be found in the GA Sections 2.2.3 "Strategy for IPR and Knowledge Management and Protection"; 3.2.14 "Innovation Management"; 3.3.2 "Industrial Involvement in Exploitation".

2.4 Dissemination of Results – Open access – Visibility of EU funding

Obligation to disseminate

Each beneficiary must disseminate their results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public. However, no dissemination may take place before a decision is made regarding possible protection (see 2.2). Other participants may object if their legitimate interests in relation to their results or background could potentially suffer harm.

Beneficiaries that intend to disseminate their results must give **advance notice** to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least **30 calendar days for publications and 15 days for oral / poster presentations**, together with sufficient information on the results they will disseminate (see also section 3). As a minimum the title, list of authors and an abstract must be supplied, before submission. Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 25 calendar days of receiving notification in the case of a publication and 10 days in case of oral or poster presentations, if they can show that their legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests (ATLAS Consortium Agreement (CA), Annex 2, Article 29.1 of the Grant Agreement (GA) as referred to in Clause 12 (AMD-678760-37)).

Notwithstanding the above, certain dissemination activities which, by their nature, must be carried out in a timely manner (e.g. social media posts, promotional articles and reports of new discoveries at sea) will be exempt from the obligation to give prior notice to all partners so as not to impede the project's dissemination strategy, provided that all ATLAS beneficiaries engaged in such dissemination are in agreement prior to such dissemination and provided that the duty of confidentiality is respected (ATLAS GA Article 29).

Open access

For Horizon 2020, providing open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to publications in funded projects is an obligation for all grants. Each beneficiary must ensure open access (OA) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results (GA Article 29.2).

Beneficiaries must:

- a. As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- b. Ensure open access to the deposited publication, via the repository, at the latest:
 - on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - within six months of publication in any other case.
- c. Ensure open access, via the repository, to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication.

There are two main routes towards open access to publications:

- A. Self-archiving (also referred to as 'green' open access) means that the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived (deposited) by the author - or a representative - in an online repository before, alongside or after its publication. Repository software usually allows authors to delay access to the article ('embargo period')

- B. Open access publishing (also referred to as 'gold' open access) means that an article is immediately provided in open access mode as published. In this model, the payment of publication costs is shifted away from readers paying via subscriptions.

For more information on open access, please consult the Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

Further details are outlined in the ATLAS DMP (D8.1): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.167407>

EU emblem

Partners are obligated and have the right to use the EU emblem when publishing and/or presenting work carried out under the ATLAS project. Any dissemination of results must display the EU emblem and include the following text:

2.5 General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679) Implications

General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679) ("GDPR") commenced on 25 May 2018, providing enhanced protection to individuals' data privacy rights. According to GDPR, any organisation storing or using personal data must clearly disclose what data is being collected and how, why it is being processed / used, how long it is being retained, and if it is being shared with any third parties. Personal data can be names, email addresses, job titles, phone numbers, and anything that allows identification of an individual.

Website:

The ATLAS website, managed by the ATLAS Project Office, has been updated to comply with GDPR by development of a Privacy Statement and cookie bar, informing website visitors about what ATLAS does with their personal data.

Mailing list:

Interested parties can join the ATLAS mailing list (and Stakeholder database) using the 'Subscribe to ATLAS news and info' button on the project website. Prior to the 25 May, the ATLAS Project Office and similarly, AquaTT as project dissemination partner, issued emails to the partnership and interested parties for consent to remain on their mailing lists. Mailing lists have been developed to keep subscribers anonymous. Mailing lists will only be used to share ATLAS related information, news and events. Personal data is stored on secure databases and will not be used /shared for any other purpose.

3. Pre-publication and dissemination requirements

According to the ATLAS CA (Article 8.3.1.1 (AMD-678760-37)), for **all types of 1) Publications and 2) Dissemination & Communication Activities** (including oral and poster presentations, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications) where ATLAS results are presented, the Prior Notice Procedure (protocol outlined below) must be applied.

PROTOCOL – Prior Notice Procedure

The main partner involved in the publication, dissemination or communication of results from the ATLAS project (owned by one or several parties) must give the other beneficiaries **advance notice** of their intention to disseminate (GA Article 29; CA Article 8.3.1.1 (AMD-678760-37)). This includes all types of publications (scientific, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed) and dissemination and communication activities whereby results from the project are disclosed.

- For **PUBLICATIONS**: At least **30 calendar days** prior to the intended results disclosure date, sufficient information (the title, list of authors, abstract, details of the journal) must be sent to the ATLAS Project Office (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk) and ATLAS Project Coordinator (Murray.Roberts@ed.ac.uk).
- For **DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES (e.g poster / oral presentations)**: at least **15 calendar days prior to the intended results disclosure**, sufficient information (the title, list of authors, abstract, details of the event) must be sent to the ATLAS Project Office (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk) and ATLAS Project Coordinator (Murray.Roberts@ed.ac.uk).
- Immediately after notification by the main author, the ATLAS Project Office will upload the submitted information to the password protected area of the ATLAS website and also email it to all ATLAS beneficiaries, reminding beneficiaries of prior notice rules.
- Any objections to the planned Publication or Dissemination & Communication activity should be sent in writing to the authors and the ATLAS Project Coordinator and Project Manager. The timeline for Publications is within 25 days after notification, and for Dissemination & Communication activities it is xx days. ATLAS beneficiaries may object if they can show that their legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed if these results are disclosed to the public, in accordance with the Grant Agreement.
- If no objection is received before the set date, the author(s) can assume that there are no objections to making the results public.

NOTE: Each time a publication is submitted (i.e. re-submitted to a different journal etc), the ATLAS Project Office should be informed and provided with the updated information.

4. Post-Publication Requirements: Continuous Reporting on Publications and Dissemination & Communication Activities

As part of the EU contractual requirements, all scientific publications (4.1), dissemination and communication activities (4.2), and exploitation activities (4.3) should be reported as part of the “Continuous Reporting” of the project in the EC Funding & Tender opportunities Portal.

PROTOCOL – EC Reporting on Publications, Dissemination & Communication Activities, and Exploitation Activities.

- Partners should keep track of all their scientific publications, dissemination & communication activities, and exploitation activities during project implementation.
- An “ATLAS Continuous Reporting Template (Excel)” has been developed by AquaTT to support the reporting of these activities (a new template was developed in October 2018 – M30).
- The ATLAS Project Office will send the Reporting Template Excel to all partners at (internal and external) reporting periods (so every 6 months) and partners are expected to complete it for all their publication, dissemination & communication and exploitation activities during the previous 6 months.
- The reporting template contains separate worksheets to report on 1) Publications; 2) Dissemination & Communication activities; 3) Patents (IPR/exploitation activities). Individual protocols for each are outlined below.
- Detailed protocols on how to report each of these (separate) activities are outlined below.

4.1 Continuous Reporting of Scientific Publications

Types of Scientific Publications: Articles in Journals; Publication in conference proceedings /workshop; (Chapter in) Book / Monograph; Thesis / dissertation.

ATLAS Partners are responsible for ensuring that all their scientific publications are uploaded to Zenodo (if not published in Gold Open Access) and the EC Funding & Tender opportunities Portal. Partners are encouraged to upload their publications as soon as available and no later than three months after the official publication date. Prior to publishing, partners must give prior notice to all other ATLAS beneficiaries (see section 3).

- Instructions how to upload your publications to Zenodo can be found in the ATLAS DMP (D8.1) and in this short tutorial: <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1MfZSdyZHS5zvmNmAGHD7ki6whNAhHN1LGKRMnbSrTBg/edit#slide=id.p3>. For more information on depositing research outputs at Zenodo please contact Stéphane Pesant (spesant@marum.de).
- Publications published in Gold open access or deposited on Zenodo (green open access) are automatically reported to OpenAIRE (so long as they include the ATLAS Grant Agreement number in the acknowledgements) and to the EC Portal. However, please note that even though they are automatically reported to the EC Portal, **they still need to be accepted and imported** (giving further details), see detailed instructions below. In addition, when you upload

a new scientific publication, please inform the ATLAS Project Office (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk), who will add the publication to the project website.

PROTOCOL – Publications Reporting

- If published in Green Open Access: Post publication, upload your scientific publications to Zenodo: instructions on how to do so can be found in the ATLAS DMP (D8.1) and in this short tutorial: <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1MfZSdyZHS5zvmNmAGHD7ki6whNAhHN1LGKRMnbSrTBg/edit#slide=id.p3>. Once it is uploaded to Zenodo, the publication is automatically uploaded to the EC Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal (through OpenAIRE) as well.
- If published in Gold Open Access: The publication is automatically uploaded to the EC Funding & Tender Opportunities (through OpenAIRE), if ATLAS is acknowledged (please make sure you include the correct acknowledgement, with the correct GA number!).
- In both cases (Green or Gold Open Access), publications will be listed as a suggested publication on the portal, and will need to be imported (= accepted) as a real ATLAS publication, including adding more details.
- Therefore, please logon to the EC Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal (instructions below) to actively import the publication and complete the missing information. Please let AquaTT (annette@aquatt.ie) know in case you don't have access to the Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal. Missing information that will need to be completed still on the EC Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal relates to:
 - Open Access: Gold or Green (when Green, indicate embargo period. When Gold, indicate processing charges). When you select 'no', you will get a warning, since all publications need to be Open Access!
 - Is it a peer-reviewed publication?
 - Is it a joint public/private publication?
- Once imported (make sure you **save** after importing!), inform the ATLAS Project Office who will then add the new publication to the publication list on the project website.
- Please add the publication and its details to the "Continuous Reporting Template (Excel) – worksheet 2. Publications" which is collected every six months by the ATLAS Project Office (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk). The internal template contains additional fields on beneficiaries involved and contact person & details, and logs each publication according to reporting period.
- The ATLAS Project Office is responsible for ensuring all publications have been transferred to the EC Participant Portal, at internal and external reporting time. AquaTT will support the Project Office and cross-check the information as required.

EC Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal (previously called Participant Portal) guide:

1) Visit the Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal (/ EC Participant Portal) by following the link below and log in (red square): <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>

2) Go to "My projects" (red square) on the left and then select "ATLAS".

3) From the "Actions" list on the right, select "Manage Project".

ACRONYM	CALL	PROGRAM	PROJECT	PHASE	ACTIONS
ATLAS	H2020-BG-2015-2	H2020	678760	Active	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Project ConsortiumManage ProjectView Proposal

4) Click on “Continuous Reporting” (red square)

5) Select the “Publications” tab in the top menu. There are two options; add “Suggested publications from OpenAIRE” or “Manually add publication”.

No.	Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proc./Book	Date of Acceptance	DOI	Repository Link	Actions
1	Article in	Structure and transport of the North Atlantic Current	Houpert, Loic; Inall, Mark; Dum	Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans	23/07/2018	10.1029/2018JC014162	10.1029/2018JC014162	✕
2	Other	Effects of changing ocean regimes on deep-sea bent	Kazanidis, Georgios; Henry, Lea		30/05/2018	10.5281/zenodo.1255842 10.5281/zenodo.1255843	10.5281/zenodo.1255842 10.5281/zenodo.1255843	✕
3	Article in	Rare Earth Element distribution in the NE Atlantic; E	Crockett, Kirsty; Hill, Emily; Abe	Frontiers in Marine Science 5	30/04/2018	10.3389/fmars.2018.00147	10.3389/fmars.2018.00147	✕
4	Article in	Zoantharians (Hexacorallia: Zoantharia) associated v	Carreiro-silva, Marina; Ocana, C	Frontiers in Marine Science	01/04/2018	10.3389/fmars.2017.00088	10.3389/fmars.2017.00088	✕
5	Article in	Niche overlap between a cold-water coral and an as	van Oevelen, Dick; Mueller, Chr	PLoS ONE 13(3) e0194659	01/03/2018	10.1371/journal.pone.0194659 10.1371/journal.pone.0194659	10.1371/journal.pone.0194659 10.1371/journal.pone.0194659	✕

We recommend you first check the list of “Suggested publications from OpenAIRE” to see if your publication has been suggested. If so, please open the “Import publication” pop-up screen by clicking on the entry, fill in the missing details and “Import” the publication (bottom of the field).

If you notice a suggested publication in the list that you know is definitely not related to the project, please ‘Discard’ the publication.

If your publication is not yet in either the suggested OpenAIRE list, or in the Project Publications list (please double-check to avoid duplicates) then click “Manually add publication”. When using the “Manually add publication” option, please provide a DOI (this is recommended, as this will automatically pre-fill most of the information) or fill-in the required information manually.

NOTE: Fields that are not automatically pre-filled but are mandatory to complete are questions on: Open Access, whether the publication is peer-reviewed and if it is a joint public/private publication.

Depending on the type of publication, the fields in the form will change (see below for “Article in Journal”).

New publication

DOI	<input type="text"/>
Type of publication	Article in Journal
Repository Link	<input type="text"/>
Link to the publication	<input type="text"/>
Title	<input style="height: 40px;" type="text"/>
Authors	<input style="height: 40px;" type="text"/>
Title of the Journal/Proceedings/Books series/Book (for book chapters)	<input type="text"/>
Number, date or frequency of the Journal/Proceedings/Book	<input type="text"/>
Relevant Pages	<input type="text"/>
ISSN/eISSN	<input type="text"/>
Publisher	<input type="text"/>
Place of publication	<input type="text"/>
Year of publication	<input type="text"/>
Is this publication available in Open-Access, or will it be made available?	<input type="radio"/> Yes - available in Green Open Access * <input type="radio"/> Yes - available in Gold Open Access <input type="radio"/> No
Is this a peer-reviewed publication?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No *
Is this a joint public/private publication?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No *

NB: Once you have added the publication (using either “Suggested publications from OpenAIRE” or “Manually add publication”), make sure you **‘save’** the overall publications page, the button is on the top right of the page.

4.2 Continuous Reporting of Dissemination & Communication Activities

ATLAS partners are encouraged to disseminate and communicate their findings to ATLAS stakeholders. When disseminating or communicating project results, partners must give prior notice to all other beneficiaries (see section 3).

The following information is required for every dissemination & communication activity and are part of mandatory EC reporting:

- **Type of activity (specify number of activities per type):** organisation of a conference or workshop, press release, popularised publication, exhibition, flyer, training, social media, website, communication campaign, participation in a conference, workshop or other event, video/film, brokerage event, pitch event, trade fair, participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects.
- **Type of audience reached (specify the number of persons per type):** scientific community, industry, civil society, the general public, policy makers, media, investors, customers.

- **Total Funding amount** for dissemination and communication activities linked to ATLAS spent until the time of reporting.

NOTE: The ATLAS Project Office and AquaTT will upload the information related to Dissemination and Communication activities from all partners to the EC Portal.

Partners must complete the “ATLAS Continuous Reporting Template (Excel)” only and NOT enter data on the Portal (tab: Dissemination and Communication activities).

PROTOCOL – Dissemination and Communication Activities Reporting

- Partners should keep track of all their dissemination and communication activities throughout the project, on a continuous basis, (preferably) using the “ATLAS Continuous Reporting Template (Excel)”.
- The ATLAS Project Office will request the completed “Continuous Reporting Template (Excel) – worksheet 3. Diss & Comms activities” from each partner, every six months.
- AquaTT are responsible for collating the information submitted by each partner into one MASTER Excel sheet and summarising the numbers required.
- The ATLAS Project Office are responsible for uploading the collated information on Dissemination and Communication activities from all partners to the EC Participant Portal.

4.3 Patents (IPR) - Exploitation Activities

ATLAS partners are responsible for ensuring that their Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and innovation activities resulting from the project are uploaded onto the EC Portal. The following information is required on Patents and IPR under the ATLAS project:

- Identification of IPR type and Confidentiality
- Type of IPR (Patent/Trademark/Registered Design/Utility Model/Other)
- Confidentiality (Yes/No)
- Application Title
- Embargo end date.

PROTOCOL – Patents (IPR) Reporting

- Partners should keep track of all their IPR and innovation activities throughout the project, (preferably) using the “ATLAS Continuous Reporting Template (Excel)”.
- Partners are responsible for uploading new IPR to the EC Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal(/ EC Participant Portal), see instructions above and below, whenever new IPR has been filed (note the EC recommends filing with the European Patent Office).
- At 6-monthly reporting stages, each partner who has filed IPR should complete the “Continuous Reporting Template (Excel) – worksheet 4. Patents (IPR)” sent by the ATLAS Project Office (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk).
- Log in to the Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home> (see instructions above on how to log above - EC Participant Portal guide: steps 1-4)
- Select the “Patents (IPR)” tab in the top menu and then click “Add IPR” (see figure below).

The screenshot displays the Horizon 2020 project management interface. At the top, a navigation bar includes various tabs: Summary for publication, Deliverables Ethics, DMP, Other Reports, Milestones, Critical Risks, Publications, Dissemination, Patents (IPR), Innovation, SME Impact, Open Data, Gender, and ABS Regulation. The 'Patents (IPR)' tab is highlighted with a red box and contains a green checkmark icon. Below the navigation bar, the 'Patents (IPR)' section is visible. It features a checkbox labeled 'This project does not have any Registered Intellectual Property Right yet'. Below this, there is a blue information icon and a note: 'Important! If a filed application is rejected by the IPR authority during the course of the EU funded action (the project's duration) then you must remove the concerned item from the IPR list'. At the bottom of the section, it states 'There are no Intellectual Property Right registered.' and includes an 'Add IPR' button. A red arrow points from the 'Patents (IPR)' tab to a 'SAVE' button located in the top right corner of the section.

NB: Once you have added the IPR information, make sure you save using the button on the top right of the page.

5. ATLAS Dissemination Resources and Activities

The importance of disseminating knowledge and results from research projects has been recognised by the EC as one of its priorities (COM(287)182 final). Dissemination of results is a contractual obligation of participation in research initiatives supported under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The specific aims of this provision are to promote knowledge sharing, greater public awareness, transparency, and education. The dissemination involves not only looking at where and when the information should be disseminated but also what should be communicated and how it should be presented.

5.1 Project Branding (Logo)

A specific project logo has been developed for project identity. Brand guidelines have been developed alongside the logo and are uploaded onto the Partner's Area of the project website. The brand guidelines detail the correct application of the logo in relation to the background, spacing, etc. The logo is and will be included in all project promotional material including the factsheet, website, etc.

Top: the logo essence, and bottom with optional elements (left with flags, and right with flags and tagline)

All logos can be downloaded from the [Partner's Area of the project website](#) or contact WP9 leader AquaTT (atlas@aquatt.ie).

5.2 Factsheet

An ATLAS project factsheet has been designed and produced for distribution. The factsheet describes the project, its main objectives, partnership, funding and expected results, and is being used as a way to raise general awareness of the project.

The factsheet is available for download from the [Partner's Area of the project website](#) and by contacting WP9 leader AquaTT. Partners are encouraged to distribute the factsheet through their networks and at relevant events.

The ATLAS factsheet can be translated into ANY language, following the protocol outlined below. As of M28 (August 2018), the ATLAS factsheet is available in English, French, Spanish, Portuguese and Dutch.

PROTOCOL – Factsheet

All partners have been provided with an electronic copy of the project factsheet for distribution (print and/or electronic) to their personal and institution network of contacts/

Partners can translate the leaflet into their own language. The protocol for translation is as follows:

1. Partner contacts AquaTT (atlas@aquatt.ie) requesting the template with English text.
2. AquaTT supplies a template with the original text in English to partner
3. Partner translates text (as laid out in the template) into their language
4. Partner then sends translated text back to AquaTT
5. AquaTT applies the translated text to the leaflet design template and publishes the designed version of the translated leaflet.

5.3 Website

A dedicated ATLAS website (part of Task 9.2) has been set up and is maintained by the ATLAS Project Office (UEDIN) following the EU Project Websites – Best Practice Guidelines with graphics and brand guidance from AquaTT. The website is a one-stop access online portal and plays multiple roles; a communication resource to promote the project, its objectives, and partnership; a communication resource to update interested parties on progress, results and outcomes and a repository for public deliverables. The public project website is visually attractive and informative and includes a link to the web-based collaborative workspace to facilitate continuous project partner communication.

The continuous updating of the website includes the Calendar of events organised by the ATLAS consortium, as well as events where ATLAS partners are represented, and any other events of interest to the partnership. The News section is regularly updated with news on the project as well as external news relevant to ATLAS. The Resources Centre houses all dissemination products and activities including open access scientific papers, articles, press releases and the project factsheet.

As of May 2018, Google analytics has been used to track traffic and monitor use of the website.

PROTOCOL – Website

The ATLAS Project Office manages the ATLAS website and updates it on a regular basis. Any partners who have feedback on the site or wish to upload materials, news or events to the website (calendar) should contact the ATLAS Project Manager (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk).

Partners are requested to include a link to the ATLAS website on their own institution websites as well as promote the ATLAS social media channels.

5.4 Social Media

Social networking is an integral part of the ATLAS communication strategy. The project is actively disseminated through Twitter (**@eu_atlas**) and Facebook (**@EuATLAS**) (both led by the ATLAS Project Office) and LinkedIn (“**ATLAS - Deep Discoveries**”) (led by AquaTT), where ATLAS relevant information is communicated.

The project Twitter account has 1083 followers, Facebook has 268 followers; 269 likes and LinkedIn has 47 members (M38).

Anyone can follow ATLAS on Twitter and Facebook, and while anyone can join the LinkedIn group, members must be approved due to LinkedIn Group Management settings. Internal and external project stakeholders are encouraged to join all forms of ATLAS social media. These channels are a forum for engagement with interested external parties and contribute to capacity building and showcasing the partnership expertise and knowledge through active discussions. For Twitter, different hashtags (#) have been and will be created for various activities, such as research cruises “#atlasatsea” and communicated to the partnership.

Other types of e-media such as Wikipedia and YouTube/Vimeo and Research Gate may be used as additional channels for dissemination in order to reach broad audiences if deemed relevant. Partners should contribute to Social Media channels where possible to ensure the timely communication of interesting activities and results, engaging and addressing all levels of ATLAS stakeholders. For more

PROTOCOL – Social Media

Twitter

Partners wishing to communicate via Twitter have the following options:

- 1) Send a short message (max. 280 characters) to the ATLAS Project Manager (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk) who can tweet from the ATLAS Twitter account on your behalf. Ideally please include an image to make it visually more attractive, and remember to include “@eu_atlas” and “#H2020” in your 280 characters.
- 2) Refer to “@eu_atlas” Twitter handle in your own tweets.
- 3) Re-tweet ATLAS tweets through your own personal accounts or your institution’s.
- 4) ATLAS Twitter account – direct access: if you anticipate a high level of tweets around a specific event or activity (e.g. an ATLAS cruise or conference session), please let the Project Manager know and we can discuss best means to manage, including sharing login access to the ATLAS Twitter account so you can tweet real time.

Facebook

Partners wishing to keep updated via Facebook, please like the page (@EuATLAS), leave comments, share and post stories.

LinkedIn

Partners wishing to communicate via LinkedIn are invited to join the group (ATLAS – Deep Discoveries) and can communicate directly with other group members. Partners are encouraged to upload photos and share their activities.

Research Gate

Partners wishing to communicate via Research Gate are invited to join the official ATLAS project page: ‘[ATLAS – A Trans-Atlantic assessment and deep-water ecosystem-based spatial management plan for Europe](#)’. Partners may follow the project or be added as a collaborator (via [J. Murray Roberts’s Lab](#)), and link their ATLAS publications, presentations as well ask questions and join discussions.

information and guidance on the use of Social Media please consult the EC publication: ‘Social Media Guide for EU funded and R&I projects’: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

PROTOCOL – ATLAS code of social media conduct

- Ensure the content is yours to share (i.e. research or opinions) or acknowledge the source accordingly
- Ensure there are no IP issues
- Refer to “@eu_atlas” and / or other ATLAS social media forms
- Use “#H2020” to acknowledge the ATLAS funding
- Utilise other ATLAS related “#”s (if you like)
- Do not use offensive language, argumentative or illegal content etc.
- Protect yourself against internet / social media bots by, blocking known bad bots; enable CAPTCHA; monitoring traffic spikes and login attempts;
- Do not engage with online trolls
- Be vigilant of (targeted) spam and phishing and do not open suspicious messages
- Make yourself familiar with the privacy and data protection policy of the social media platform you are using
- Be aware of the risks of social media!

5.5 Newsletters

ATLAS has a dedicated project newsletter targeting an external audience, which is developed and distributed on a half-yearly basis. Each ATLAS newsletter highlights key project results, information about the case studies and scientific cruises. It also contains an article on the ATLAS consortium (e.g. The Advisory Board) and a “young scientists’ corner” to enable PhD students and postdocs to communicate their work to a more general audience. The newsletter is sent to the project partners, individual WPs stakeholder database contacts, existing media channels, and any other interested individuals. The ATLAS project website stores the [newsletter archive](#). Readership statistics are compiled by AquaTT during reporting periods and as needed.

PROTOCOL – Newsletter

AquaTT designs, develops and distributes the ATLAS newsletter, based on ideas and input from partners.

As the newsletter is considered time-sensitive dissemination material, it is exempt from the prior notification rule according to Article 8.3.1 of the ATLAS Consortium Agreement (CA), defined in CA Article 8.3.1.1. However, a reasonable time will be allowed for possible objections to any content. In case one has an objection, the objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications.

Partners are expected to send the newsletters to their own contacts and networks for optimum distribution and dissemination.

5.6 Press releases

News of the project is disseminated regularly, making use of a range of publications and services. Press releases are issued to appropriate media outlets (trade press, journals, web portals) to ensure that industry, civil society organisations, policy-making authorities, and the wider community are aware of the project, its objectives and, later in the project, its outcomes. The strategy is intended to ensure that there are publicity and media coverage at local, regional, European and international levels. WP9 leader

AquaTT has several existing channels and networks for disseminating news, i.e. Cordis, Alpha Galileo, LinkedIn groups, technology platforms, relevant EC projects and initiatives (e.g. COLUMBUS), etc. which ensures a broad awareness of the project across the spectrum of relevant stakeholders. Other partners are encouraged to publish articles and press releases at the regional, national and international level, making use of their own communication networks and channels.

PROTOCOL – Press Releases

AquaTT takes the lead in writing press releases based on partner's inputs and news. Partners should notify AquaTT if they think there is news worthy of an official project press release. AquaTT will also monitor project progress and identify news items.

Once approved, press releases will be disseminated using the channels mentioned above, and any other relevant means. They are also uploaded to the project website and all partners are encouraged to distribute at a national or regional level. Where necessary the partners can adapt the press releases to customise them to their audience and if needed translate the articles.

Partners may also initiate the writing of press releases (e.g. local, national). In this case, AquaTT can offer support for writing and editing and can provide graphics and images if required. Partners are asked to provide a short summary in English if the original communication is in another language.

Partners who publish any article / press release at a regional or national level must send a copy to the WP9 leader AquaTT (atlas@aquatt.ie) and where possible provide metrics to demonstrate uptake by other news channels/readership.

5.7 PowerPoint Template

ATLAS PowerPoint templates for oral and poster presentations have been developed to use at internal and external events when presenting the ATLAS project and/or its outcomes.

All templates are available for download from the Partner's Area of the project website.

In addition, AquaTT has developed three standard sets of ATLAS slides that are available introducing the key elements of the project:

- 1 Slide – A flash slide presenting the basic facts about the project
- 3 Slides – With 2 additional slides on the project and partnership
- 10 Slides – A more detailed presentation with further detail on the project

Partners are encouraged to adapt the slides and/or add more slides to suit the target audience. Partners should respect the slide master template (background, font, layout) when building new slides to ensure a consistent project branding. Where partners do update the slides, translate the slides or add new slides, please send a copy to the WP9 leader (AquaTT) so that they can be added to the master archive of slides available for the project in case other partners might benefit from using them.

The PowerPoint presentation pack is updated when needed, based on feedback from the partnership. All templates were updated in M25 (May 2018).

Partners should always ensure that the EU H2020 credit/disclaimer slide is present on any presentation.

PROTOCOL – PowerPoint Template

Partners should use the ATLAS PowerPoint Presentation pack when presenting the project and/or its outcomes at internal and external events to support project branding and recognition.

Templates for oral and poster (portrait and landscape) presentations are available to download from the Partner's Area of the project website: <https://www.eu-atlas.org/resources/atlas-partners-document-area/atlas-dissemination-materials>

Choose to insert "new slide" and pick your preferred content template.

Partners can also choose to use any of the introductory slides when presenting the project.

The introductory slides and the ppt template are available from the Partner's Area of the website.

Partners are asked to provide a copy of any new slides they develop.

5.8 Other resources and tools

Videos and New Visual Media

An introductory video was developed for the dissemination and promotion of the ATLAS project to the wider public, at the beginning of the project (M9). This video is available on the ATLAS website as well as on the YouTube channel:

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UChT_uQfwZX_S9cmWHOc_DhA and has been widely disseminated through ATLAS and partners' social media as well as through all the dissemination channels currently used within the project.

Individual Work Package videos have been developed by UEDIN and are available on the ATLAS website under the MEDIA tab: <https://www.eu-atlas.org/media-library/atlas-video> and on the ATLAS YouTube channel (link above).

Additional ATLAS videos available from the project website and YouTube include: Mingulay Video (M28); ATLAS at the UN conference on BBNJ (M29); ATLAS partner David Johnson at the UN HQ (M29).

Videos will be added to the YouTube channel as they become available and should be widely distributed by the ATLAS consortium.

A further ATLAS video will be created over the last 18 months of the project and input from all partners will be sought to best capture the work across the consortium. Production of the ATLAS Final Video began at the 4th General Assembly (April 2019). Please contact the Project Office for further details (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk).

Educational tools

As part of Task 9.4, specific targeted public outreach activities, an educational programme and workshop on the ATLAS theme and resources including visual media have been developed by Dynamic Earth.

ATLAS Educational portfolio (D9.4) developed by Dynamic Earth with support from UEDIN researchers and ATLAS Project Office and AquaTT was published in April 2019 (M36) and includes:

- A school show for Primary School Pupils (including a transcript and a compilation video)

- Activity sheets for family drop-in engagements (topics include ocean acidification; pressure in the Deep; Technology used in the deep-sea; Hydrothermal vents)
- A 'reef survey' mat featuring a cold-water coral reef
- Video and image resources from the Amundsen Cruise illustrating 'life on a research ship'
- Demo version of ROV simulator
- Fly-through videos of Case Study locations using Geovisionary
- 6 educational pop-up banners for the 'ATLAS Exhibition Stand'

Selected resources are also available in Spanish, German, French and Dutch.

All educational resources are available to download from the Education tab on the project website: <https://www.eu-atlas.org/education/education-packs>. *Other Promotional Material*

WP9 has a modest budget to develop new visual media (visuals, video, animations, infographics etc) for the project. The partnership has the opportunity to be creative and consider how best to communicate to different target audiences. If you have an idea for new material, please contact AquaTT (atlas@aquatt.ie) or the ATLAS Project Manager (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk).

6. ATLAS Knowledge Management and Knowledge Transfer

In its broad-based innovation strategy for the EU, the European Commission identified the importance of improving knowledge transfer between public research institutions and third parties, including industry and civil society organisations, as one of ten key areas for action (<http://ec.europa.eu/invest-inresearch/pdf/downloaden/knowledgetransferweb.pdf>). ATLAS will employ a proven Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology in order to effectively address this key aspect of facilitating project impacts.

Knowledge Management is the process of identifying, capturing, organising, analysing, sharing and distributing knowledge to ensure its availability and relevance for future users. Several work packages in ATLAS are involved in knowledge management: WP7 - Policy Integration to Inform Key Agreements; WP8 - Open Science Resources for Stakeholders; and WP9 - Dissemination, Knowledge Transfer and Outreach. More information on knowledge and data management methodologies can be found in the DMP (D8.1).

Knowledge Transfer (KT) is the overall process of moving knowledge between knowledge sources to targeted potential users of knowledge. KT consists of a range of activities that aim to capture and transmit knowledge, skills, and competence from those who generate them to those who will transform them into added value outcomes. It encompasses both commercial and non-commercial activities such as research collaborations, consultancy, licensing, spin-off creation, researcher mobility, and publications. While financial benefits can be expected, KT helps focusing research being conducted on the wider needs of society and industry. The ultimate end benefit of successful KT is the application and influence of knowledge on targeted communities with greater impact (short and long term) across the triple helix of academia, industry and society ([http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release MEMO-07-127_en.htm?locale=en](http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-07-127_en.htm?locale=en)).

ATLAS will implement the **Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology** originally developed in the FP7 MarineTT project, and further developed and applied by the H2020 COLUMBUS project (GA# 652690). This methodology has been applied in many FP7 and Horizon²⁰²⁰ projects such as AQUAEXCEL, AQUAEXCEL²⁰²⁰, AquaInnova, ARRAINA, ATLAS, COEXIST, COMMON SENSE, ECsafeSEAFOOD, MaCuMBA, MG4U, ParaFishControl, REvived water and STAGES.

The methodology focuses on '**Knowledge Outputs**' (KOs), where a KO is described as "a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a scientific project. It is not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge" (*definition developed by AquaTT in the context of Knowledge Management in the MarineTT project*).

The methodology consists of three phases:

a) Collect

b) Analyse (including assessing knowledge and profiling Target User)

c) Transfer (including developing a plan and measuring impact)

The implementation of this methodology will ensure that all outcomes from the project, including scientific outputs, new methodologies, data, protocols and experimental approaches as well as de-novo knowledge and new strategies, are captured and appropriately transferred (taking into consideration IPR) to relevant stakeholders. Thus, it will be possible to fast-track that knowledge with the potential to be adopted by others working in the field, thus advancing (i) scientific development in

the research community and (ii) ocean governance by policy makers. Furthermore, it will allow for the identification of opportunities for exploitation, ensuring that new knowledge is brought to market on the fastest route possible.

All knowledge capture, assessment and transfer activities will be done in line with the ATLAS Consortium Agreement, respecting privacy and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) requirements, thus providing partners with the security needed to successfully transfer their findings.

All partners will contribute to the project's Knowledge Management and Transfer activities by adhering to the protocols and assisting in the collection of Knowledge Outputs and transfer of high potential Knowledge Outputs to targeted end-users.

Over the course of the project, two Knowledge Transfer Activity Reports will be developed, one has been delivered in M24 and the second one is due in M48. The Knowledge Transfer activities of the project, and associated key outputs, will be published on the ATLAS public website, after having ensured any IP / protection issues. It was foreseen that any relevant Knowledge Outputs will be taken up in the "Marine Knowledge Gate" <http://www.kg.eurocean.org> to ensure visibility and availability to stakeholders; however, the host is not accepting Knowledge Output submissions for immediate upload currently, as their updated platform has not yet been published online. All ATLAS data will be effectively managed via WP8, details on management and storage of the different research outputs are outlined in the DMP (D8.1).

The knowledge transfer three-step methodology for the purpose of the ATLAS project is further described below.

6.1 KT: Collect

The first phase of KT involves the capturing of Knowledge Outputs in an internal KO Template (Annex I), which includes information on potential application(s), impact, end-users and exploitation. Quality control measures will be performed, to ensure that the KO(s) can be clearly understood by others working in different disciplines. Each partner will treat information from other partners as confidential unless otherwise stated and not disclose it to other parties unless the information is publicly available.

PROTOCOL – Collect:

1. AquaTT will complete a Knowledge Output Template (KOT) in collaboration with each ATLAS WP leader, collecting what they deem as key outputs from the project.
2. If the WP leader thinks another partner is better placed to provide the requested information, then the AquaTT team will contact the relevant partner(s) and complete the KOT with them.
3. AquaTT will ensure the following:
 - no typographical/editing errors;
 - the short title of the KO(s) is adequately informative;
 - the knowledge description of the KO(s) is comprehensive enough to adequately understand the nature of the KO and to determine its possible application;
 - potential end-users of the KO will be identified and listed, as well as their potential application;
 - it will be clarified if the KO(s) is publicly available or is subject to issues of Intellectual Property (which would have an effect on transfer potential).
4. If deemed necessary, AquaTT will contact the KO author/s and the Project Coordinator to discuss the KO and identify if there is anything missing or unclear.

6.2 KT: Analyse

The second phase involves understanding the positioning of the KO(s) in the current landscape, identifying the eventual impact and target users that should be the focus of transfer. This information can then be used to inform the development of a Knowledge Output Pathway (by the various responsible WP leaders) and ensure that the KT activities carried out are impactful.

The following protocol is in place in relation to the Analysis phase:

PROTOCOL – Analyse:

1. AquaTT assures all KO fields are complete and validated. Where further clarifications are required, AquaTT requests more information from the authors/creators of the KO.
2. Where input is required, KO(s) will be prioritised by AquaTT with support from ATLAS WP leaders by ranking the KOs 'low', 'medium', or 'high' level of potential impact after consulting with scientific experts from the consortium with background/experience relevant to specific KO(s) (e.g. the ATLAS Steering Committee and Advisory Board).
3. Other partners may be asked to review or comment on the KO(s), for example to assist in the identification of end-users and potential applications, when necessary.
4. A Knowledge Output Pathway will be developed, mapping out the step or steps required to carry each KO to its eventual impact.
5. The first individual(s) along the pathway considered the "Target User", is identified.

Note: The "Target User" is not necessarily the end user or beneficiary of the Knowledge Output; rather they can be the stepping-stone needed for the Knowledge Output to progress towards an Eventual Impact.

Knowledge Output Pathway

6.3 KT: Transfer

The Target User (identified in phase 2) is profiled to gain information and insights to inform a successful **Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP)**. These profiles will be used to identify and customise the appropriate messages, communication channels, materials and tools to be used to develop a successful Knowledge Transfer Plan.

Knowledge Transfer activities will take place during the ATLAS project and will include:

- Participation at industry and policy events to promote engagement of the appropriate stakeholder groups (T7.1, T7.2).
- ATLAS data uploaded and shared via appropriate platforms including the EMODnet portals to ensure visibility and availability to end-users (T8.2)
- Fostering exchange of ideas and collaboration among the scientific community and other sectors, including the Blue Growth sector (T7.4)

The **impact** of ATLAS Knowledge Transfer activities will be measured using indicators, that could include: uptake and application of knowledge following these activities; number of publications; number of spin-offs, patents, grants etc; number of collaborations; number of research agreements with SMEs; number of companies who use the knowledge generated from the project. If knowledge has been transferred, it does not mean that it has been applied. Impact measurements should be based on whether the transfer impact was achieved, e.g. were changes observed in a Target User's knowledge attitude or behaviour. At the end of the project, ATLAS will produce a compendium presenting the projects knowledge outputs and their effective transfer and impacts (short and long term) on different end-user groups.

The following protocol in relation to the Transfer phase will be applied:

PROTOCOL – Transfer:

1. Whenever necessary, the ATLAS Steering Committee will be consulted to discuss the most appropriate way to transfer the KOs (exploitation mechanisms and exploitation partner(s)), whenever necessary.
2. The partner transfer office (/tech transfer office) is responsible for examining IP issues to ensure protection and implement appropriate actions when needed.
3. Knowledge Transfer activities will be carried out (see section 7.2: external events), depending on the KO, its associated end-user and possible applications, and resources available.
4. Impact of the activities carried out will be measured (quantitatively / qualitatively).

7. ATLAS Stakeholder Engagement and External Events

7.1 Stakeholders

ATLAS is a large and complex project with multiple stakeholder groupings. The project targets a wide community including:

- Scientific/academic community (within and outside the ATLAS consortium)
- Policy makers (national, European, international level)
- Industry (oil and gas, non-Blue Growth)
- Society (school children, families, general public)

Stakeholder engagement is managed across the project work plan, at different times, for different purposes and varying target audiences. A centralised stakeholder database facilitates communication with all stakeholders involved in ATLAS and is being held by the ATLAS project office and leaders of WP9 (AquaTT).

Depending on their level of engagement, different dissemination and exploitation mechanisms are employed. The stakeholder database aims to facilitate dialogue, relationship building and process generation that takes place between that ATLAS consortium and other organisations involved or interested in the project. It is maintained and updated for the duration of the project.

Following General Data Protection Regulation (EU 2016/679) (“GDPR”) ATLAS stakeholders have to consent to the storage of their details from 25 May 2018 (see also section 2.5). Stakeholder information is being stored on a secure database and is used to email ATLAS related information, news and events, only. Personal data is not used for any other purpose or shared with any other organisation.

PROTOCOL – ATLAS Stakeholder Database

Interested parties must consent to the storage of their information (for the purpose of the ATLAS project) and can be added to the ATLAS Stakeholder Database by:

- 1) Registering on the ATLAS website using the sign-up button to ‘Subscribe to ATLAS news and info’
or
- 2) Requesting (via email) to be added. Requests can be sent to the ATLAS Project Office (EU-Atlas@ed.ac.uk) or WP9 leader AquaTT (marieke@aquatt.ie; annette@aquatt.ie).

Stakeholders will receive regular updates, news, invitations to events etc, relevant to ATLAS from the Project Office and WP9 leader AquaTT.

7.2 External Events

Conferences, seminars, workshops and other meetings are very useful forums to consult with ATLAS target audiences in a face-to-face capacity and to address issues relevant to the work done in the project. International and sector relevant conferences, meetings, etc. are frequently attended to communicate the results of the project to the maximum number of persons.

Events are included in the project calendar by the Project Office on the ATLAS website. All activities, including attendance to external events should be logged locally by individual partners and reported in the template developed by AquaTT during EC reporting stages (see above).

7.2.1 Public Outreach Activities

All partners have a responsibility to engage the public in their research activities and results and take advantage of the considerable potential for public interest that ATLAS generates. Partners are encouraged to initiate dissemination activities that are appropriate for their respective contributions and AquaTT can provide support as required. Examples include live webcam broadcasts, cruise blogs, art exhibitions, institute open days etc.

Under Task 9.4, led by Dynamic Earth (DE), specific targeted public outreach activities and resources have been developed. These include:

- Dynamic Communication Products, including an ROV simulator and interactive cold-water model, for the Oceans gallery at DE that provide insight into the Atlantic deep-water environment and the aims of the objective of the ATLAS project.
- Educational Programme and workshop on the major ATLAS themes have been created for marine educators and adopted by Dynamic Earth as part of their annual outreach programme, with the aim of engaging around 8,000 people in Scotland with ATLAS via participation in regional science festivals (March-September 2019). It will also run across the busy summer period at Dynamic Earth, expected to reach at least an additional 7,000 people (July-August 2019).
- Outreach activities and resources including a 'Reef Survey' Activity; a series of public engagement sheets and activity packs for educators and an ATLAS 'School Show'. The concepts illustrated by the sheets are listed below:
 - The importance of the ocean for humans and all life on Earth
 - Ocean acidification
 - Pressure in the Deep
 - How ROVs use different sampling tools
 - Technology used in deep-sea exploration including ROVs, Gliders and Landers/Moorings
 - Hydrothermal vents (inspired by the discovery of new vents off the Azores by the IMAR-UAz team on a Blue Azores Expedition organised by the Oceano Azul Foundation, in cooperation with the Waitt Foundation and National Geographic PRISTINE SEAS, and in partnership with the Regional Government of the Azores).
- A dynamic ATLAS exhibition stand aimed at a family audience was developed for informal activities and will be used by DE for outreach at regional science festivals and community events in remote parts of the UK and potentially elsewhere. It includes six banners designed to communicate ATLAS science themes, 360° videos with cardboard 'viewers' and public-friendly blogs.
- All educational and digital outreach materials developed by DE are available to download from the Education tab on the ATLAS website (April 2019): <https://www.eu-atlas.org/education/public-engagement> for partners to share. The resources will also be uploaded to the ATLAS community page on Zenodo, ensuring that they will be accessible by all project stakeholders, beyond the project's lifetime and increasing the ATLAS legacy (<https://zenodo.org/record/2652408#.XMarDzBKl71>). Dynamic Earth's website will be updated to link to the ATLAS education area and external organisations/groups such the Sea Change project, POGO, UK Schools Ocean Resources Hub and Scuttlebutt will be invited to share the

link, enabling public outreach and the communication of deep-sea topics and ATLAS research across Europe as well as the US and Canada.

- “Meet-the-scientist” Outreach Training workshop for researchers. Dynamic Earth offered best-practice advice and outreach guidelines to host outreach events and develop their public engagement skills at the 4th ATLAS General Assembly (April 2019). A further “Meet-the-scientist” showcase event is planned to take place in March 2020.

ATLAS partners should inform the Project Office of their planned outreach activities in order to give an overview of overall ATLAS outreach activities, enabling identification of gaps in the dissemination and knowledge communication strategy which can then be addressed accordingly. This will optimise resource allocation while maximising impact.

All public engagement and outreach activities must be reported during (internal and external) reporting periods (see section 4). Please add the details of such outreach activities to the “Continuous Reporting Template (Excel) – worksheet 3” which is collected every six months by the ATLAS Project Office (Eu-Atlas@ed.ac.uk).

Research outputs and dissemination materials will be communicated and shared with existing educational programmes.

PROTOCOL – Guidelines for Engaging the public ‘Do’s & Don’ts’ (developed by Dynamic Earth)

- Avoid ‘crisis’ language – emphasise urgency for change but highlight positive examples of what can be done.
- Focus on how ocean *sustains* human wellbeing & all life on Earth.
- Avoid talking about the ocean as an economic resource.
- Expand understanding of ocean systems, building on existing knowledge.
- Emphasise disruption to entire ecosystems, not just key species.
- Stress negative outcomes for all populations, *not* just coastal communities.
- Avoid a generic ‘we’ for responsibility of ocean conservation.
- Introduce wider pollution issues, not just plastics and oil spills.
- Highlight links between marine conservation and prosperity.
- Discuss how policy changes are important rather than just individuals taking action.
- Avoid romanticising the vastness/mystery of the ocean.

Reference: Lindland, E. and Volmert, A., 2017. Getting Below the Surface.

7.2.2 Industry Knowledge Exchange

Industry workshops, organised in WP6 and WP7 (e.g. [Ocean Business 2019](#)), will be used to explore data sharing possibilities with industry within ATLAS data management framework (WP8) as a basis to reduce costs to business of conducting expensive environmental assessments. Industry will also be asked to give expert opinion on potential adaptive management measures such as mitigation, biodiversity offsetting, habitat banking and restoration to facilitate development while protecting biodiversity specific to each Case Study.

7.2.3 Policy Knowledge Exchange

ATLAS partners are actively engaged with national and international policymakers. A series of Science-Policy engagement events to consult with policymakers and implement a Science-Policy interface all take place within the framework of WP7 and are excellent means to carry out transfer of policy-related Knowledge Outputs and key messages from the project. Three ATLAS Science-Policy Panels have taken place, bringing the latest results and Blue Growth opportunities identified in the project directly to policymakers. ATLAS has a strong trans-Atlantic partnership in Canada and the USA where both government and academic partners interact with ATLAS through shared cruises, staff secondments, scientific collaborations and work to inform Atlantic policy development.

7.3. ATLAS Final Event & Project Compendium

The project achievements will amongst others be presented at the final ATLAS General Assembly (M47) to important stakeholders from the EU deep sea community, decision makers and research institutes.

In addition, a project compendium will be produced as part of Task 9.3, showcasing ATLAS Key Messages and Outputs, their effective transfer and impacts on different end-user groups.

8. Links with Other Projects

ATLAS endeavours to establish and maintain effective links with other projects and initiatives that are relevant, to promote complementarity and to avoid overlap. ATLAS specifically collaborates and interacts with:

- **AtlantOS** (2015-2019) develops in-situ Atlantic Ocean Observations for a better management and sustainable exploitation of maritime resources.
- **BENTHIS** (2012-2017) assesses the health status of EU marine benthic ecosystems for Good Environmental Status and develops new tools to assess effects of bottom trawling and sustainable management plans to reduce these impacts.
- **COLUMBUS** (2015-2018) ensures accessibility and uptake of research marine research knowledge outputs by end-users. ATLAS makes use of the outcomes of COLUMBUS in relation to the Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology that is being applied in ATLAS.
- **DiscardLESS** (2015-2019) develops tools and strategies to reduce bycatch and drafts new policy guidelines for bycatch mitigation.
- **MIDAS** (2013-2016) identifies scale and duration of possible impacts of mineral mining on deep-sea ecosystems and develops solutions and best practice codes for policy and legal frameworks.
- **NACLIM** (2012-2017) quantifies predictability on inter-annual to decadal timescales of N Atlantic climate related to ocean surface state.
- **MERCES** (2016-2020) assesses methods, quantifies value and defines governing framework for the effective restoration of different degraded marine habitats.
- **SponGES** (2016-2020) develops an integrated ecosystem-based approach to preserve and sustainably use deep-sea sponge ecosystems of the North Atlantic.

ATLAS and its sister H2020 projects **SponGES** and **MERCES** had a session on '[Ocean Basin Scale Research](#)' at the [4th World Conference on Marine Biodiversity, Montréal, Canada, 13-16 May 2018](#). The session was chaired by Murray Roberts (ATLAS Coordinator) and Ellen Kenchington (SponGES Co-Coordinator). The team also worked together closely on public engagement activities during the week and hosted a booth for visitors.

9. DEP Validations and Recommendations

Each update of the Dissemination and Exploitation plan has been and will be validated by the partnership. The DEP functions as an operational manual and is revised at 18-month intervals.

10. Glossary

“ATLAS” A trans-Atlantic assessment and deep-water ecosystem-based spatial management plan for Europe.

“Access rights” are the user rights (incl. Licenses) to results or background of project partners (<http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/>).

“Application” refers to the process of converting scientific and technological advances into useable/marketable goods or services. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Background” is information and knowledge (including inventions, databases, etc.) held by the participants prior to their accession to the Grant Agreement, as well as any intellectual property rights which are needed for carrying out the project or for using results. Regarding intellectual property rights for which the application was filled before the accession of the participant to the Grant Agreement are included. The fact that participants are legal entities is important in this respect. If a specific department of a university or company is involved in a project, the background will be that of the whole university or company (subject to its relevance to the project), not just that of the specific department (unless the department constitutes a legal entity and is the participant). This is important as a participant may have to grant the other participants in the project access rights to the background of other departments under certain conditions (ftp://ftp.cordis.europa.eu/pub/fp7/docs/ipr_en.pdf).

“Deliverables” A deliverable is a physical output related to a specific objective of the project, e.g. a report, publication, newsletter, tool, website, or conference. A distinction can be made between external deliverables, which are created for customers and stakeholders, and internal deliverables, which are produced for the purpose of executing the project, and are usually only needed by the project team and the commissioning authority. Both types need to be specified and listed in the work package plan (http://ec.europa.eu/eahc/management/Fact_sheet_2010_03.html).

“Dissemination” is defined as a planned process of providing information on the quality, relevance, and effectiveness of the results of programmes and initiatives to key actors. It occurs as and when the results of programmes and initiatives become available. This activity happens at both project and programme level and involves the active participation of intermediary “relay” bodies (http://ec.europa.eu/education/programmes/llp/guide/valor/what_en.html).

“End-Users” are persons/organisations that have an application for a knowledge output(s) of an RTD project. The knowledge output may have undergone several revisions/adaptations through the value chain before reaching/being relevant to the needs of the end-user. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Exploitation” consists of mainstreaming and multiplication. Mainstreaming is the planned process of transferring the successful results of programmes and initiatives to appropriate decision-makers in regulated local, regional, national or European systems. Multiplication is the planned process of convincing individual end-users to adopt and/or apply the results of programmes and initiatives (http://ec.europa.eu/education/programmes/llp/guide/valor/index_en.html).

“Impact” is the effect of the uptake and use of the knowledge output of the target community and how it influences other actions. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Knowledge” means expert skill, information or understanding that imparts an ability to cause the desired result; it is not readily available and may be outside the public domain. Knowledge encompasses technical information such as discoveries, concepts, methodologies, models, research, development and testing procedures, the results of experiments, tests and trials, manufacturing processes, materials, formulae, formulations, processes, research or experimental results, techniques and specifications, quality control data, analyses, and reports. Knowledge differs from data or information in that new knowledge may be created from existing knowledge by extension of logic. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Knowledge Management” comprises a range of practices used by organisations to identify, create, represent, and distribute knowledge for reuse, awareness, and learning. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Knowledge Outputs” are types of different knowledge items produced in the course of research projects. For the purposes of MarineTT, Knowledge Outputs are categorised under 16 types – Technical Handbook/Manual, Scientific Publication, Report, Book/Review, Case study, RTD Protocol, Prototype, Product, Service, Standards, Database/Directory, Software/Modelling Tools, Guidelines, Learning module, Multimedia, and Other. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Knowledge Transfer” is the process of creating, organising, capturing/sharing/distributing knowledge to ensure its availability for future users. Knowledge transfer encompasses both commercial and non-commercial activities such as research collaborations, consultancy, licensing, spinoff/spinout creation, researcher mobility, and publications etc. Knowledge transfer aims to support mutually beneficial collaborations between universities, businesses, and the public sector. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Participant” is a legal entity taking part in an indirect action and having the rights and obligations defined in the Grant Agreement entered into with the European Commission (on behalf of the European Union) (ftp://ftp.cordis.europa.eu/pub/fp7/docs/ipr_en.pdf).

“Technology Transfer” is the process of skill transferring of technology-related interaction intended to make products of R&D other creative activities available, to ensure that scientific and technological developments are accessible to a wider range of users. These users can then further develop and exploit the technology into new products, processes, applications, materials or services. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Transfer Mechanism” refers to channels of interaction (mechanisms) through which knowledge transfer is effectuated. Such mechanisms include Networks, Continuing professional development, Contract research, Licensing, Spin-offs, and Teaching. Other channels may include public outreach by means of scientific or popular media, movement of people (recruitment, temporary secondment, mentoring, student placement, etc.), and sharing of facilities. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Uptake” is the action of using and incorporating knowledge. Uptake can occur at any stage along the entire value chain and is not limited to primary end-users. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Use” is the utilisation (direct/indirect) of the results in research activities, which are not part of the project, as well as utilisation for further development, creation, and marketing of a product or process. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

“Value Chain” is a chain of activities for a firm operating in a specific industry. Products pass through all activities of the chain in order, and at each activity, the product gains some value. As an example - steps in the value chain can include R&D, Design of Products/Services/Processes, Production, Marketing & Sales, Distribution and Customer Service. The chain of activities gives the products more added value than the sum of the independent activity's value. Definition according to MarineTT (FP7 project number 244164).

References & Useful Guides

H2020 Programme Guidance, Social Media guide for EU funded R&I projects (2018)

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

H2020 Online Manual (2019), Grants, Grant Management, Dissemination & Exploitation of results.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm)

D8.1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.167407>): Pesant, Stéphane; Roberts, Murray; Simpson, Katherine; Junge, Claudia. 2016. ATLAS Deliverable 8.1 - Data Management Plan. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.167407

Annex 1 – ATLAS Knowledge Output Table (KOT) Template

ATLAS Knowledge Outputs will be captured using an internal KOT template which helps to obtain a proper in-depth and critical understanding of each KO. The KOT is presented in the format of an Excel file and consists of four worksheets: 1. an introduction to the KOT (KOT; see **Figure 1S**), 2. Definitions (see **Figure 2S**), and 3. the KOT (see **Figures 3-5S**) and 4. TRL levels. The objective of the KOT is to be able to identify KOs and collect them consistently.

Figures 3S, 4S and 5S show the different sections within the KOT. **Section 1** is collecting 'General Information' about the KO like Short Title, Knowledge Type, KO Description, Contact Information, Open / Restricted Access, Link to KO. **Section 2** contains information on 'Application and End-user identification' like Sectors & Subsectors, Potential End User, Potential Application, IPR Protection. **Section 3** collects 'Exploitation' information like Status, End User Description, Impact and Exploitation, and **Section 4** contains 'Comments' like Submission date and additional notes.

Knowledge Output Table (KOT) Template

INTRODUCTION

ATLAS employs a Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology to ensure that all relevant knowledge coming out of the project will be collected, transferred and taken up by relevant users so **we deliver impact and create value** from our activities.

More information on ATLAS Knowledge Management and Transfer methodology can be found in the ATLAS DEP (D9.1; V3).

As a first step in the process, all (finalised) project **KNOWLEDGE OUTPUTS*** will be captured in this internal template (see worksheet 4: Knowledge Output Table), along with their detailed descriptions. Your responses will help us to assess whether a Knowledge Output is of high potential to deliver impact and to get insight into what steps can be taken next to ensure your Knowledge Output reaches the users who can take it up.

We would like to emphasise that you can share your KNOWLEDGE OUTPUTS without compromising IP or affecting your potential to publish later.

In case of any questions, please contact Annette Wilson (annette@aquatt.ie) or Marieke Reuver (marieke@aquatt.ie)

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Figure 1S. An introduction to the Knowledge Output Table (KOT).

DEFINITIONS	
Knowledge	Intellectual property rights and related know-how, information, data and other intellectual assets. Technical information including discoveries, concepts, methodologies, models, research, development and testing procedures, the results of experiments, tests and trials, manufacturing processes, materials, formulae, formulations, processes, research or experimental results, techniques and specifications, quality control data, analyses. Knowledge is not limited to scientists and is not limited to technology information. Knowledge differs from data or information in that new knowledge may be created from existing knowledge by extension of logic. <i>(Definition developed by AquaTT in the context of the MarineTT project (April 2012))</i>
Knowledge Output	A "Knowledge Output" for the purposes of this project is the term used to describe a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a research project. It is not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge. <i>(Definition developed by AquaTT in the context of the MarineTT project (April 2012))</i>
Knowledge Transfer	Knowledge transfer is the process of creating, organising, capturing/sharing/distributing knowledge to ensure its availability for future users. Knowledge transfer encompasses both commercial and non-commercial activities such as research collaborations, consultancy, licensing, spinoff/spinout creation, researcher mobility, and publications etc. Knowledge transfer aims to support mutually beneficial collaborations between universities, businesses and the public sector. <i>(Definition developed by AquaTT in the context of the MarineTT project (April 2012))</i>
Knowledge Type(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * exploitable scientific result *exploitable technical result * scientific publication * report * book/review * RTD protocol/technical manual * guidelines/standards * training activity/learning module * software/modelling tools * product * prototype * services/tools * multimedia * data (if data, please specify where they are held in column B) * other (if other is chosen, please try to clarify in column A or B)

Figure 2S. Definitions (not all shown) of terminology used in the KOT (see Figures 3S-5S).

Short Title	Knowledge Type	Knowledge Output Description	Contact Information	Open/ Restricted Access?	Link to Knowledge Output
<p>Please provide a short and concise title to describe the Knowledge Output.</p> <p>(For Knowledge Output definition, see 'Definitions' worksheet)</p>	<p>DROPDOWN MENU - Please choose one option.</p>	<p>Try to give a comprehensive description, making the Knowledge Output fully understandable to a non-expert.</p> <p>For example, what are the key characteristics of the Knowledge Output? What is innovative about it? How does it progress beyond the current state-of-the-art / evidence base? Do you have a justifying body of evidence, or are there contradictory results?</p>	<p>Please provide contact details of the most relevant person to provide further information if required on the Knowledge Output.</p> <p>If the beneficiary/owner of the Knowledge Output differs from the contact person then please indicate so.</p>	<p>*Please refer to Section 3, 4 and 5 of the ATLAS Data Management Plan (D8.1) which outlines accessibility to datasets.</p> <p>If there are no plans to make the output publicly available now or in the future, please state 'Restricted Access'.</p> <p>If not open /publicly available, please provide further details on the justification(s) for such restrictions.</p> <p>If the status of the data will change over time from open to restricted, or vice versa, please provide details.</p>	<p>If you can provide a link to the Knowledge Output then please do so, e.g. website address, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), scientific journal details, Patent Number, etc.</p>

Figure 3S. KOT. Section 1 – General Information about the KO.

Sectors & Subsectors	End User	Potential Application	IPR Protection
<p>DROPDOWN MENU - Chose as many sectors as you think would benefit from the application (uptake) of this Knowledge Output.</p> <p>More than 1 sector / subsector can be applicable, choose as many options from the dropdown list as you think are relevant.</p> <p>For each sector chosen please use a separate row.</p>	<p>DROPDOWN MENU - Select the type of end user category that you think could take up this Knowledge Output once it has been fully developed, marketed, installed, etc.</p> <p>There can be more than 1 type of End User, e.g. Scientific Community, Policy Makers, Industry, Environmental Managers, Education, Other.</p>	<p>Per identified end user, please identify possible applications of your Knowledge Output. How can the End User use/apply your Knowledge Output?</p> <p>For each application identified, please use a separate row, linking it with the relevant End User in the previous column.</p> <p>Try to be as specific as you can and include an indication of timescale to application (short, medium, long-term).</p>	<p>Please indicate whether you have applied IPR to this Knowledge Output (applied for a patent, copyright etc), or not.</p> <p>Please leave blank if no IPR has been applied.</p> <p>Please indicate "yes" if IPR has been applied to this Knowledge Output (applied for a patent, copyright etc) or "no" if not applicable.</p> <p>If yes, please provide details</p> <p>Please insert "unsure" if IPR has not been considered yet.</p>

Figure 4S. KOT. Section 2 – Application and End-user identification.

Status	End User Description	Impact	Exploitation	Submission Date	Notes
<p>Please identify whether the Knowledge Output is finalised, is still being generated or whose status/future is unknown.</p> <p>Consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -If the Knowledge Output relevant to the scientific community, please indicate whether it is conclusive, requires further investigation or if there are contradictory results available. -If the Knowledge Output could inform evidence based policy, please indicate what further validation/contextualisation would be required. -Does the Knowledge Output progress beyond the state-of-the-art? -Is more research or demonstration needed to validate or commercialise the prototype/ results? If yes, please provide details. -If the Knowledge Output is technology based, please indicate TRL level (1-9) 	<p>Refers back to column I (End User). Here we would like more detailed information on each End User you have previously identified.</p> <p>Try to be as specific as possible, for example for ‘Policy Makers’ indicate the exact type and level also, e.g. European Commission – DG Research & Innovation / Directorate E (Health) / E1 Strategy</p>	<p>Please indicate any impact that has been achieved already.</p> <p>If there has been no impact yet, what do you think could be the potential resulting impact of this Knowledge Output once it has been transferred to and taken up by the End User(s)? Try to quantify where possible.</p> <p>Indicators of impact could be (examples, there could be other); proven increased productivity, more environmental-friendly solutions, a patent grant, the creation of a spin-off, new research agreements with SMEs, etc.</p>	<p>This field is directly related to the identified End Users & Potential Applications, as the exploitation mechanism depends on these. In this field indicate past and current activities to reach your identified End User.</p> <p>Please also indicate under which workpackage these activities have/will take place- this is to ensure no overlap between what the project intends to do and what ATLAS can offer in terms of KT.</p> <p>Examples are: publications, events and networking, collaborative research / researcher mobility, consultancy / training courses, licensing, new business / spin-offs, etc</p> <p>Please include web addresses, reference material, project reports so further investigation can be carried out.</p>	<p>Please enter the submission date of this Knowledge Output, in dd/mm/yyyy.</p>	<p>Any extra information which you deem relevant but is not included in other fields.</p> <p>This can include confidential information which shouldn't be made public but would be useful for doing the analysis. If so, clearly indicate CONFIDENTIAL</p>

Figure 5S. KOT. Section 3 (Exploitation) and 4 (Comments).

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		CO Confidential restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement		
		CI Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC		

Authors (Partner)	AquaTT			
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